

A receptor-based assay to study the bitterness masking effect of yeast extracts

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Abstract

Yeast extracts (YEs) are widely used by the food industry for the formulation of foods and beverages, as they bring a natural combination of flavour molecules, including aroma-active and non-volatile compounds (taste-active compounds). Adding a touch of umami, some richness or a typical flavour signature, YEs are used as ingredients to mask the bitterness of some food products. In the present work, using functional calcium mobilization assays, we demonstrated the ability of two different YEs (YE1 and YE2) and the ribonucleotide adenosine 5' monophosphate (AMP) to stimulate heterologously expressed human bitter taste receptors named TAS2Rs. We then observed that YE1 inhibits the response of two TAS2Rs stimulated by control agonists. Our data demonstrate that the bitterness masking effect of YEs is a molecular mechanism occurring at the receptor level.

Keywords: yeast extract, bitter taste, GPCR, bitter taste receptor TAS2R, inhibition

Introduction

Yeast extracts (YEs) are valuable ingredients commonly used for their wide variety of powerful taste properties in many food and beverage applications. Derived from fermentation, the molecular composition of YEs is very complex and provides flavours in different ways. YEs are an important source of taste-active compounds generated upon breakdown of polymeric molecules (polysaccharides, proteins, nucleic acids, etc.). Among them, the 5' purine ribonucleotides guanosine 5'-monophosphate (GMP) and inosine 5'-monophosphate (IMP) are known to synergize with glutamic acid and elicit umami taste on their own [1]. YEs also contain adenosine 5' monophosphate (AMP), which has been identified as a bitter taste inhibitor by sensory experiments conducted in humans [2, 3]. Bitter taste perception is one of the five basic taste qualities, generally causing aversion to avoid ingestion of potentially toxic compounds. Bitter compounds are detected by a specific subset of taste receptor cells localized in the mouth and characterized by the expression of the TASTE 2 receptor (TAS2R) gene family. TAS2Rs belong to the family of class A G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs). They all possess a heptahelical transmembrane domain (TMD) connected by three extracellular loops (ECLs) and three intracellular loops (ICLs), with a short extracellular N-terminus and an intracellular C-terminus [5-7]. The human genome contains 25 genes coding TAS2Rs, which are able to detect thousands of chemically diverse compounds. AMP has been demonstrated to block taste receptor transduction activated by bitter tastants [8]. In addition, some bitter blockers have been identified to act at the TAS2R level to reduce the bitterness intensity of a number of food products [5]. In this study, to further investigate the mechanism of the bitterness masking effect of two YEs (YE1, high content in AMP and GMP; YE2, high content in IMP and GMP) and AMP, we functionally expressed 25 human TAS2Rs using an *in vitro* mammalian expression system coupled to calcium imaging analysis.

Experimental

All experiments were conducted *in vitro* using HEK293T cells stably expressing the chimeric G protein G α 16gust44, which harbours 44 gustducin-specific sequences at its C terminus [9]. Combining functional expression of TAS2Rs and calcium mobilization assays, we followed two different approaches. First, we examined the direct interaction of YEs and AMP with the 25 human TAS2Rs. Next, we measured the potential bitterness masking effect of YE1 towards two specific TAS2Rs stimulated by control agonists.

YE samples and chemicals

The two YEs were supplied by Biospringer by Lesaffre (Maisons-Alfort, France). The first one, YE1, is characterized by high contents of AMP and GMP, while the second one, YE2, derived from YE1 by enzymatic conversion of AMP to IMP, contains high amounts of IMP and GMP. Other chemical compounds, such as AMP, MgSO₄, and aristolochic acid, were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Saint-Quentin Fallavier, France). The compounds were dissolved in buffer C1 (130 mM NaCl, 5 mM KCl, 10 mM HEPES, 2 mM CaCl₂, 10 mM glucose, pH 7.4). Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM) and all tissue culture media components were purchased

from Life Technologies (St Aubin, France). The Fluo4-AM calcium indicator was obtained from Molecular Probes (St Aubin, France).

Generation of human TAS2R expression vectors

The amino acid sequence of human TAS2Rs were obtained from the online NCBI Protein database. The synthetic DNAs encoding TAS2Rs were codon optimized for humans (GeneWiz) and subcloned into the pcDNA4/myc-HisA plasmid (Invitrogen) between the *EcoRI* and *NotI* restriction sites. To improve protein expression in mammalian cells, the QBI SP163 translational enhancer sequence (MAX) was added before the start codon. Membrane targeting was increased using the first 45 amino acid residues of rat somatostatin receptor 3 (SST3) located in the receptor N-terminus. Finally, the FLAG epitope was added to the C-terminus to detect the expression and subcellular localization of TAS2Rs by immunocytochemical techniques.

Functional heterologous expression assays

HEK293-G α 16-gust44 cells were seeded at a density of 35,000 cells per well on clear bottom poly-D-lysine-coated 96-well microtiter black plates in DMEM supplemented with 2 mM GlutaMAX, 10% dialysed foetal bovine serum, penicillin/streptomycin and G418 (400 μ g/mL) at 37°C, 6.3% CO₂, and 100% air humidity. After overnight growth, the cells were transiently transfected with each of the TAS2R expression plasmids using Lipofectamine 2000™ (Life Technologies) according to the manufacturer's protocol. For the negative control, cells were transfected with empty pcDNA4/mycHisA vector. Twenty-four hours later, the cells were loaded with the calcium-sensitive dye Fluo4-AM in the presence of 2.5 mM probenecid for 1 hour and washed twice with C1 solution. Calcium responses of cells were recorded after application of test substances in a Fluorometric Imaging Plate Reader, FLIPR (Molecular Devices) after excitation at 488 nm and emission recorded at 510 nm. For direct application, YE1 and YE2 were tested at different concentrations between zero and 1000 μ g/ml (1000 ppm) and from zero to 100 μ M (347 ppm) for AMP. For the pre-treatment experiment, washed cells were bathed in YE1 solutions ranging from zero to 3000 μ g/mL for ten minutes, rinsed once with C1 buffer and subjected to calcium imaging measurements after automatic injection of the control agonist.

Data were collected from at least two independent experiments carried out in duplicate. For the calculation of dose-response curves, signals of wells receiving the same concentration of test substances were averaged. The fluorescence changes of the corresponding mock-transfected cells were subtracted and normalized to background fluorescence. Dose-response relationships and EC₅₀ values were calculated in SigmaPlot (Systat Software) by nonlinear regression using the function $f(x) = \min + (\max - \min)/(1 + (x/EC_{50})^{-Hillslope})$.

Results and discussion

To identify human bitter taste receptors activated by YEs or AMP, we transiently transfected the cDNAs of TAS2Rs in HEK293-G α 16-gust44 cells. Transfected cells were loaded with a calcium-sensitive dye and then subjected to bath application of YEs or AMP, while changes in cytosolic calcium levels were recorded in a fluorometric imaging plate reader. The response profile of TAS2Rs shows that YEs and AMP are able to activate nine TAS2Rs (Table 1). Among them, we confirmed the activation by all compounds of TAS2R10 and TAS2R14, which are known to be broadly tuned receptors. Interestingly, YE1, which contains AMP, and AMP alone activate the same subset of TAS2Rs, except for TAS2R30, TAS2R43 (known for their intermediate agonist spectra) and TAS2R50 (narrowly tuned TAS2R). We confirmed that YE1 and AMP increase the calcium response of TAS2R16 and TAS2R38, which were identified as taste receptors specifically recognizing a distinct class of chemicals (β -glucopyranosides and isothiocyanates, respectively). Interestingly, these two TAS2Rs are associated with variability in taste detection linked to gene polymorphisms. Conversely, for YE2, a restricted response profile and the highest EC₅₀ values were measured for TAS2R10 and TAS2R14, suggesting that this IMP-enriched YE (instead of AMP) contains weaker bitter agonists than YE1.

Table 1: Response profile of 25 TAS2Rs stimulated with YEs and AMP. EC₅₀ values are indicated.

	Receptor	Alias	Compound		
			YE1	YE2	AMP
1	TAS2R1		—	—	—
2	TAS2R3		—	—	—
3	TAS2R4		186 µg/mL	—	254 µM
4	TAS2R5		—	—	—
5	TAS2R7		153 µg/mL	—	213 µM
6	TAS2R8		—	—	—
7	TAS2R9		—	—	—
8	TAS2R10		392 µg/mL	907 µg/mL	109 µM
9	TAS2R13		—	—	—
10	TAS2R14		32 µg/mL	> 1000 µg/mL	69 µM
11	TAS2R16		32 µg/mL	—	79 µM
12	TAS2R19*	TAS2R48	—	—	—
13	TAS2R20	TAS2R49	—	—	—
14	TAS2R30	TAS2R47	108 µg/mL	—	—
15	TAS2R31	TAS2R44	—	—	—
16	TAS2R38		37 µg/mL	—	16 µM
17	TAS2R39		—	—	—
18	TAS2R40		—	—	—
19	TAS2R41*		—	—	—
20	TAS2R42*		—	—	—
21	TAS2R43		—	—	30 µM
22	TAS2R45*		—	—	—
23	TAS2R46		—	—	—
24	TAS2R50		232 µg/mL	—	—
25	TAS2R60*		—	—	—

* receptors remaining orphan; —, no response

To investigate the bitter masking effect of YEs in greater detail, we focused our experiment on YE1, which shows more interactions with TAS2Rs. We asked whether YE1 could inhibit the activation of two receptors (TAS2R7 and TAS2R14) stimulated by their agonist controls. For this purpose, we challenged TAS2R7- and TAS2R14-expressing HEK293-Gα16-gust44 cells with several pre-treatment concentrations of YE1 followed by injection of increasing concentrations of MgSO₄ and aristolochic acid, respectively (Figure 1). The ten-minute pre-treatment of HEK293-Gα16-gust44 cells with the highest YE1 concentration of 3000 µg/mL led to both a right shift of the dose-response curves, corresponding to a decrease in half-maximal response (EC₅₀ value), and a reduction of maximal signal amplitude for the two tested receptors. These results suggest a loss of potency/affinity and a decrease in efficacy, revealing competitive and non-competitive binding mechanisms of YE1 towards receptor and agonist interactions. Compared to TAS2R14, we observed that TAS2R7 is more sensitive to YE1 application, as this shift is clearly visible at a concentration of 300 µg/mL.

Figure 1: Dose-response curves of TAS2R7 and TAS2R14 with YE1 inhibition of agonist controls. HEK293T-Gα16gust44 cells were transfected with TAS2R7 (A) or TAS2R14 (B). After transfection, cells were treated for ten minutes with increasing concentrations of YE1 diluted in C1 buffer: without YE1 (dark rows) or with 90 µg/mL (cyan rows), 300 µg/mL (orange rows), 900 µg/mL (green rows) and 3000 µg/mL (grey rows) YE1. Then, agonist controls (MgSO₄ and aristolochic acid for TAS2R7 and TAS2R14, respectively) were applied to the cells, and fluorescence changes were monitored for calcium imaging analyses using an automated plate reader. Changes in fluorescence ($\Delta F/F_0$) were plotted semi logarithmically upon agonist application (mean \pm SEM). Experiments ($n = 2$) were performed in triplicate.

Conclusion

Using transient expression of human bitter taste receptors in a mammalian expression system, we demonstrated that YEs and AMP stimulate distinct sets of human TAS2Rs. We then tested YE1, a YE rich in AMP, for its ability to inhibit bitter taste receptors and observed a specific inhibition for two of them: TAS2R7, which has been implicated in metal ion detection, and TAS2R14, a broadly tuned bitter taste receptor.

Interestingly, we found that activation of the bitter taste receptor by YE1 occurred at low concentrations, while inhibition required higher concentrations, suggesting complex mechanisms of molecular interactions probably linked to the mixture of constituents present in the extract. Taken together, our findings are relevant to determine the concentration of YEs used in formulations and open the way to better understand the masking of bitter off-taste by YEs.

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